

Triggers

PHENIX DAQ system is capable to collect up to ~6 thousand events per second. If the collision event rate is higher than that, PHENIX uses special triggers to tag more interesting events (e.g. ones with a high pT photon), keeping some fixed DAQ bandwidth fraction to collect minimum bias or other high rate events, using trigger scale down (or prescale) mechanism.

The Table below gives explanation for the general triggers used by PHENIX in Runs 9-16.

BBCLL1	Generated by coincidence of signals from North and South BBC, with particular requirement for the number of PMTs fired, e.g. BBCLL1(>0 tubes) ; by default it includes a collision z-vertex cut of $ z < 30\text{cm}$; also it may not include vertex cut, i.e. BBCLL1(>0 tubes) novertex or include narrow vertex cut (varying from ± 10 to $\pm 15\text{cm}$), i.e. BBCLL1(>0 tubes) narrowvtx . In dA and pA collisions BBC is also used to select most central collisions (usually 5-10% centrality) requiring higher threshold on the number of PMTs fired on A (south) side, e.g. BBCLL1(> 1 tubes) central narrowvtx , with >1 tubes on the north and higher threshold on the south. In low energy or asymmetric collisions, one side trigger was used, e.g. BBCLL1_N(>1 tubes) for north side only
ZDCLL1	Generated by coincidence of signals from North and South ZDC; may be implemented with wide (ZDCLL1wide , implying $ z < 150\text{cm}$) or narrow (ZDCLL1narrow , implying $ z < 30\text{cm}$) vertex cut; “Blue logic” coincidence trigger is ZDCNS (no vertex cut). North and South triggers are generated and can be used separately, e.g. ZDCN for north arm
ERTLL1	Generated by energy in 2x2 or 4x4 overlapping sets of EMCal towers with summed energy above predefined threshold. There are 3 versions of 4x4 triggers allowing three different thresholds, in order from lowest to highest thresholds: ERTLL1_4x4c , ERTLL1_4x4a and ERTLL1_4x4b . 2x2 trigger can be used separately (usually with threshold lower than in 4x4 triggers), i.e. ERTLL1_2x2 or in coincidence with signal in RICH detector, with fired EMCal and RICH trigger modules geometrically aligned, used for electron data, i.e. ERTLL1_Electron or ERTLL1_E
MPC	Generated by energy in 4x4 overlapping sets of MPC towers with summed energy above predefined threshold. Typically, threshold in 4x4B triggers was set up to $p_T > \sim 3.5 \text{ GeV}/c$ in $\sqrt{s} = 500 \text{ GeV}$ runs, and to $p_T > \sim 2.5 \text{ GeV}/c$ in lower energy runs; and lower thresholds in 4x4a and 4x4c. It is generated separately in North and South arms, allowing setting three different thresholds (similar to ERT triggers, and similarly denoted as A, B, C), e.g. MPC_N_A for trigger version A in North arm. If arm (N or S) is not mentioned, it implies N S, e.g. MPC_A

MUIDLL1	Generated by different (programmable) combinations of five MUID stations, with hits in different stations geometrically aligned. It is generated separately in North and South arms. MUIDLL1_N1D and MUIDLL1_S1D use “deep” tracks for muons, penetrating to the last MUID plane, in North and South, respectively. MUIDLL1_N1H and MUIDLL1_S1H use “shallow” tracks for hadrons, which stop before the last MUID plane. MUIDLL1_N2D and MUIDLL1_S2D are programmed for di-muon data, looking for two “deep” tracks.
RPC	Generated by RPC1 and/or RPC3 detectors, separately in North and South arms. RPC1 is subdivided radially onto B (inner) and C (outer) sectors. RPC3 is subdivided onto A (inner), B (middle) and C (outer) sectors, with separate trigger capability.
MUON_SG	Generated by hits in MuTr planes, aligned allowing different bent (sagitta). It is generated separately in North and South arms, with sagitta ≤ 1 strip for the high pT track momenta (SG1) or ≤ 3 strips for lower pT track momenta (SG3), e.g. MUON_N_SG1 for high pT track momenta in North arm. It may include RPC, e.g. MUON_N_SG1_RPC3A
FVTX_HighMult	Generated when the number of hits in FVTX is higher than predefined threshold
UltraPeriph or UPC	Generated with ZDC & !BBC in coincidence with ERT_2x2. Instead of ERT_2x2, it can be in coincidence with MUIDLL1_2D triggers, e.g. UltraPeriphMuon2DSouth , or with MPC trigger, e.g. UltraPeriphMPC . Two ZDC arms may be included as N S (as in case with ERT2x2) or as N&S (as in case with Muon2D)

In physics data taking we also used triggers which are products of logic operation between these triggers (formed in GL1 board), e.g. **ERT4x4c&BBCLL1**, which requires both ERT4x4c and BBCLL1 trigger fired.

Due to occasional problems with LL1 trigger boards, sometimes direct “Blue Logic” scheme was used to generate any particular trigger, instead of LL1, e.g. ERT instead of ERTLL1.